

Development of an automated system for controlling temperature and humidity in production rooms.

Assistant of the Department of General Technical Subjects of the Asian International University Murodov Oybek Turakulovich

Annotation: *The article discusses automated temperature and humidity control systems in production rooms. First, general information about cooling systems, their types and properties is provided, and typical and various designs of temperature and humidity control systems for production rooms are analyzed, and then the implementation of these technologies in such systems is considered.*

Keywords: *temperature, humidity, production room, automatic control system.*

Annotation: *Maqolada ishlab chiqarish xonalari temperaturasi va namligini avtomatlashtirilgan boshqarish tizimini ishlab chiqish usullarini tashkil qilish ko'rib chiqilgan. Boshida avtomatlashtirilgan sovutish tizimining turlari va hossalari to'g'risida umumiy ma'lumot berilgan bo'lib, shuningdek ishlab chiqarish xonalarning temperaturasi va namligini odatiy hamda turli xil boshqarish tizimlarini qurish usullari tahlil qilingan, keyinchalik esa ushbu usullarni shu tizimlarda qo'llanilishi ko'rib chiqilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *harorat, namlik, ishlab chiqarish xonasi, avtomatik boshqarish tizimi*

Аннотация: *В статье рассматриваются автоматизированные системы управления температуры и влажности в производственных комнат. Вначале выдано общая информация про систем охлаждения их виды и свойства а также проанализировано типовое и различные построения систем управления температурой и влажностью производственных комнат, а далее рассматривается внедрение данных технологий в подобные системы.*

Ключевые слова: *температура, влажность, производственная комната, система автоматического управления.*

In the modern world, namely in the age of high technology, there remains a need for workers and employees to create comfortable working conditions. The main goals of the ventilation system are to provide the premises with a microclimate, as well as purify the air from harmful substances. By supplying a manufacturing plant with clean air at a comfortable temperature for the working personnel, work efficiency increases. As part of this trend, there is a need to automate the ventilation system. Current developments help provide better working conditions.

There are several types of ventilation systems, which are classified as follows:

- Method of air pressure and movement;
- Purpose – supply and exhaust;
- Service area – general and local;
- Design – channel and without channel.

Natural ventilation is the simplest type of ventilation, since ventilation occurs naturally and does not require special equipment.

There are situations when the power of natural ventilation is not enough and then there is a need to install artificial ventilation. The peculiarity of its work is that, the use of additional equipment that facilitates the forced movement of used air, replacing it with clean air, as well as maintaining the specified air parameters. The distinctive quality of such systems is air treatment, namely air purification, heating, cooling and humidification.

The purpose of controlling the ventilation system is to ensure and maintain the required air quality standards in the working area of the premises. Local automation is usually used to control the ventilation system. One of the most important disadvantages of such regulation is that it does not take into account the real air and heat balance of the building, as well as weather conditions. Thus, we can say that the ventilation system is not operating optimally.

By implementing optimal control of the ventilation system, you can not only increase operating efficiency, but also reduce the cost of energy resources. But for this it is necessary to use a complex of software and hardware.

Using a computer, you can find the optimal operating mode and determine the appropriate control action. As a result, the computer and the complex, consisting of software and hardware, form an automated ventilation control system. The role of a computer can be either a control panel for the supply ventilation system or a computer with a modeling program, which, based on the data obtained, establishes the optimal operating mode of the ventilation system.

Automatic control system – a set of devices designed to obtain a finished product from initial raw materials by automatically changing one or more parameters of the control object. In the case of a supply ventilation system, the finished product is air with specified parameters (temperature, humidity, etc.) in the production room.

The basis of the automatic control system for supply ventilation, as in any control system, must include feedback. Control actions are generated based on information obtained using sensors located at the facility. Each automatic ventilation control system is developed based on air treatment technology. The supply ventilation system can include both a heater (air heating) and an air conditioning system, which must be reflected when designing the automation.

Picture 1

In accordance with the standards, the mandatory control parameters are:

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-3

- Temperature and pressure in the common pipelines and at the outlet of each heat exchanger;
- Temperature of the outside air supplied after the heat exchanger, as well as the temperature in the room;
- Standards for harmful substances in the exhaust air (gases, combustion products, non-toxic dust).

When designing an automatic system, remote control is often provided; this is necessary to change the basic parameters of the system. This control is carried out using converters or sensors, the values of which can be displayed on the control panel or computer monitor.

One of the main functions that needs to be implemented is the “start sequence”. To ensure normal start-up of the supply ventilation system, it is necessary to take into account:

- Preheating of the heater. If you do not start warming up the air heater in advance, cold air can trigger the antifreeze protection. Thus, when starting the system, you should open the supply air dampers, open the water heater valve and warm up the heater. Typically, this function should be activated when the outside temperature is below 12 °C.
- Preliminary opening of air dampers. This is due to the fact that not all dampers, when closed, can withstand the pressure drop caused by the operation of the fan.
- Distribution of electric motor starting moments. This function is necessary in an automated ventilation system since asynchronous electric motors often have high starting currents. If you start the fans and air damper drives at the same time, then due to the heavy load on the electrical network, the voltage will drop significantly and the engines will not start

Many important functions that need to be provided for when designing an automatic control system for supply ventilation are the “stop sequence”. When shutting down the system, the following must be considered:

- Delay for stopping the supply air fan in systems with an electric heater. After removing the voltage from the heater, it should be cooled for some time using a supply air fan.

Based on the above options, you can create a cyclogram of the operation of the automatic control system (Figure 2.):

CONCLUSION

The presence of a ventilation system is necessary to ensure air exchange inside the building by removing excess moisture, heat, and harmful substances. Its presence is one of the main conditions for ensuring life. If there are no types of ventilation systems in the room, this is harmful to the human body, harmful substances are not removed, and leads to the formation of fungi, since condensation forms in the absence of air exchange.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). Zamonaviy ta'limda axborot texnologiyalari va ularni qo'llash usul va vositalari. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(11), 481-486.
2. Муродов, О. Т. (2023). РАЗРАБОТКА АВТОМАТИЗИРОВАННОЙ СИСТЕМЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ТЕМПЕРАТУРЫ И ВЛАЖНОСТИ В ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕННЫХ КОМНАТ. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(26), 91-95.
3. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). INFORMATIKA DARSLARINI TASHKIL ETISHDA INNOVATSION USULLARDAN FOYDALANISH. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(32), 194-201.
4. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). INFORMATIKA FANINI O'QITISHDA YANGI INNOVATSION USULLARDAN FOYDALANISH METODIKASI. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(34), 130-139.
5. Turakulovich, M. O. (2023). DEVELOPMENT AND INSTALLATION OF AN AUTOMATIC TEMPERATURE CONTROL SYSTEM IN ROOMS. *International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development*, 10(12).
6. MURODOV, O. T. (2023). INNOVATIVE INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES AND NEW METHODS AND TOOLS FOR THEIR APPLICATION IN TODAY'S EDUCATION. *International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development*, 10(12).
7. Muradov, O. (2024, January). APPLICATION OF BASIC PRINCIPLES AND RULES OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES TO EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES. In *Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 3, No. 1, pp. 46-55)*.
8. Muradov, O. (2024). BASIC PRINCIPLES AND RULES OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. *Models and methods in modern science*, 3(1), 84-93.
9. Muradov, O. (2024). APPLIED TO THE CURRENT TRAINING PROCESS REQUIREMENTS. *Инновационные исследования в науке*, 3(1), 54-63.
10. Murodov, O. (2024). DEVELOPMENT OF AN AUTOMATED PARAMETER CONTROL SYSTEM ROOMS AND WORKSHOPS BASED ON CLOUD TECHNOLOGIES. *Академические исследования в современной науке*, 3(2), 16-27.
11. Murodov, O. (2024). DEVELOPMENT AND INSTALLATION OF AN AUTOMATIC TEMPERATURE CONTROL SYSTEM IN ROOMS. *В SOLUTION OF SOCIAL PROBLEMS IN MANAGEMENT AND ECONOMY (Т. 3, Выпуск 2, сс. 91–94)*.

12. Муродов, О. (2024). РАЗРАБОТКА АВТОМАТИЧЕСКОЙ СИСТЕМЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ТЕМПЕРАТУРЫ И ВЛАЖНОСТИ В ПОМЕЩЕНИЯХ. В CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES (Т. 3,
13. Murodov, O. (2024). TA'LIM TEXNOLOGIYALARINING ILMIY-NAZARIY ASOSLARI. В SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM (Т. 3, Выпуск 3, сс. 155–160).
14. Murodov, O. (2024). INNOVATSION YONDASHUV ASOSIDA INFORMATIKA VA AXBOROT TEXNOLOGIYALARI FANINI O'QITISH JARAYONINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH. В THEORETICAL ASPECTS IN THE FORMATION OF PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES (Т. 3, Выпуск 4, сс. 77–81).
15. Murodov, O. (2024). INNOVATIVE INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES AND NEW METHODS AND TOOLS FOR THEIR APPLICATION IN TODAY'S EDUCATION. В CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF EDUCATION AND INNOVATION (Т. 3, Выпуск 2, сс. 83–92).
16. Murodov Oybek Turakulovich. (2024). Development of an automated system for controlling temperature and humidity in production rooms. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 403–409.
17. Махмудова Нигора Хикматовна. (2024). Преподавание профильных предметов в начальной школе . *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(2), 436–444.
18. Isomova, FATQ (2022). THE IMPORTANCE OF SPEECH DEVELOPMENT ACTIVITIES IN PREPARING CHILDREN FOR SCHOOL EDUCATION IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(1), 947-949.
19. G'aniyevna, P. R. F. (2022, June). МАКТАБГА ТАЙЙОРЛОВ GURUHLARI UCHUN SAVODXONLIKKA O'RGATISH MASHG'ULOTLARIDA, A''HARF-TOVUSHINI O'RGATISH METODIKASI. In *E Conference Zone* (pp. 38-41).
20. Tojiddinovna, I. F. A. (2024). Tarbiya turlari va ularning shaxs kamolotiga ta'siri. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(2), 429-435.
21. Tajiddinovna, I. F. (2024). Types of education and their impact on personality development. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(2), 469-475.
22. Исомова, Ф. Т. (2024). Виды образования и их влияние на развитие личности. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(2), 461-468.
23. Tojiddinovna, I. F. A. (2024). МАКТАБГАЧА ТА'LIMDA "ILK QADAM" DASTURI. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 603-608.
24. Tajiddinovna, I. F. A. (2024). FIRST STEP PROGRAM IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 609-614.
25. Tajiddinovna, I. F. A. (2024). THE ISSUE OF EDUCATION IN PRIMARY EDUCATION. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 615-620.
26. Tojiddinovna, I. F. A. (2024). МАКТАБГАЧА ТА'LIM JARAYONIDA BOLALARNING IJTIMOY MOSLASHUVI. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 590-595.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-3

27. Рузиева, М. (2023). ТАРЖИМА ПЛАТФОРМАСИ-МУТАРЖИМ ЛИСОНИЙ ТАФАККУРИНИНГ КЎЗГУСИ. Наука и технология в современном мире, 2(20), 37-39.
28. Рузиева, М. Я., & Эргашева, Т. Ш. (2022). МЕТОДЫ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ УЧЕБНЫХ СЛОВАРЕЙ НА УРОКАХ РОДНОГО ЯЗЫКА И ЧТЕНИЯ В НАЧАЛЬНЫХ КЛАССАХ. Вестник науки и образования, (2-2 (122)), 29-32.
29. Ravshanovna, X. S. (2023). PEDAGOGIK MULOQOT O'QUV JARAYONI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING MUHIM OMILI. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(8), 131-139.
30. Khalilova, S. (2022). PHILOSOPHICAL ASPECTS OF GLOBALIZATION. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 28, 6-11.
31. Ravshanovna, X. S. (2023). Bo 'lajak o'qituvchi pedagogik muloqot usullarini rivojlantirish texnologiyasining zamonaviy modellari va ularni qo'llash metodlari. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(9), 223-234.
32. XALILOVA, S. (2021). JAHON PEDAGOGIKASIDA ZAMONAVIY PEDAGOGIK MULOQOT VA MILLIY PEDAGOGIK MULOQOT USLUBLARIGA TRANSFORMATSIYASI. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz)*, 1(1).
33. Ravshanovna, K. S. (2023). Factors Affecting the Formation of a Positive Attitude to the Learning Activity in Students. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(9), 116-122.
34. Ravshanovna, X. S. (2023). Globallashuv sharoitida o'quvchilar aqliy-ruhiy qiyofasini shakllantirishda muloqot uslublarning ahamiyati. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 100-106.
35. Ravshnovna, K. S. (2023). THE ROLE OF THE CULTURE OF COMMUNICATION IN MODERN EDUCATION AND EDUCATION. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 3(3), 356-361.
36. Ravshanovna, X. S. (2022). BO'LAJAK O'QITUVCHILAR VA O'QUVCHILAR O'RTASIDAGI MULOQOT JARAYONI VA UNGA QO'YILADIGAN TALABLAR. *Лучший инноватор в области науки*, 1(1), 814-819.
37. Ravshanovna, X. S. (2023). O'qituvchi kasbiy faoliyatida pedagogik muloqot usullarining o'zlashtirish jarayoniga ta'siri va ahamiyati. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(10), 803-816.
38. Xalilova Shaxlo Ravshanovna. (2024). The teacher's views on the technologies for the development of pedagogical communication methods. *МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА*, 2(2), 368–376.
39. Халилова, Ш. Р. (2024). Технологии разработки методов педагогического общения в образовательном процессе сделанный увеличивать технологии. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 261-268.
40. Ravshanovna, X. S. (2024). PEDAGOGLAR TOMONIDAN DARSDA VA DARS DAN TASHQARI MUHITDA QO'LLANADIGAN PEDAGOGIK MULOQOTNING USLUBLARI. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 2(1), 126-134.

41. Ravshanovna, X. S. (2023). PERSONAL DEVELOPMENT AS A SOCIAL-BIOLOGICAL PHENOMENON, AS AN OBJECT AND SUBJECT OF THE PEDAGOGICAL PROCESS. *International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development*, 10(12).
42. Ravshanovna, X. S. (2023). Teachers by before school education organization in pupils passable training in the process to the children applied pedagogical communication styles classification. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 3(5), 237-243.
43. O'ktam qizi Buxoro, S. M. (2022). BOLANING NUTQINI RIVOJLANTIRUVCHI O 'YINLAR. *PEDAGOGS jurnali*, 1(1), 484-486.
44. Oktam's, S. M. (2023). Methods and Tools of Speech Development of Small Group Children in Preschool Education Organization. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(9), 104-108.
45. O'ktam qizi Shukurova, M. (2023). Speech grow up in training using interactive methods. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(10), 357-360.
46. O'ktam qizi Shukurova, M. (2023). The importance of genres of folklore in the education of preschool children. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 96-99.
47. Shukurova, M. (2023). METHODS AND METHODS OF INCREASING CHILDREN'S SPEECH IN A PRESCHOOL ORGANIZATION. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 477-480.
48. Madina O'ktamovna Shukurova. (2024). " Growing children's speech in the process of introducing them to the environment and nature ". *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 130-135.
49. Shukurova, M. (2024). OILADA FARZAND TARBIYASIDA OTANING ROLI. ZAMONAVIY TARAQQIYOTDA ILM-FAN VA MADANIYATNING O 'RNI, 3(2), 162-167.
50. O'ktamovna, S. M. (2024). MAKTABGACHA TA'LIMDA TABIAT BURCHAGINI TAYYORLASH. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 661-667.
51. O'ktamovna, S. M. (2024). EXTRACURRICULAR ACTIVITIES IN PRIMARY GRADES. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 654-660.
52. O'ktamovna, S. M. (2024). PREPARATION OF THE NATURE CORNER IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 675-681.
53. Баротов, Ш. Р. (2023). НАУЧНО-ПРАКТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ СОЗДАНИЯ ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ СЛУЖБЫ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. *ЛКИИСИ РАН, МАПН, 2023-267 с.*, 13.
54. Баратов, Ш. Р., & Сабирова, Д. А. (2016). Социальный интеллект как необходимое качество педагога. *История российской психологии в лицах: Дайджест-ISSN 2415-7953 (РИИЦ)*, (6).
55. Баротов, Ш. Р. (2018). Психологик хизмат: Магистрлар учун дарслик. Т.: "Наврўз" нашриёти, 344.

56. Баротов, Ш. Р. (2015). A role of social intellekt and social competence in professional development of a teacher in the intense training system. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences*, 3(4), 43-48.
57. Баротов, Ш. Р. (2012). Социальный Интеллект: Структура и Функции. *Психология XXI столетия*, 2, 153-158.
58. Баротов, Ш. Р. (1995). Ўқувчи шахсини ўрганиш усуллари. Т.: Ўқитувчи, 57.
59. Баротов, Ш. Р. (2021). Из опыта внедрения концепции психологической службы в Узбекистане. “XXI АСР ПСИХОЛОГИЯСИ” МАВЗУСИДАГИ ХАЛҚАРО ИЛМИЙ-АМАЛИЙ АНЖУМАНИ МАҚОЛАЛАР ТЎПЛАМИ, 5.
60. Баротов, Ш. Р. (2017). Психологическая служба образования: от теории к практике.(Учебно-методическое пособие). Бухара: Дурдона.

